

TOTALITARIAN OBSTACLES AND MODERN CHALLENGES IN THE STUDY OF WORLD LITERATURE¹

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the importance of teaching samples of the world literature at literature lessons in a secondary school against the background of modern challenges in the world and its main educational aspects. In the learning process, the role and importance of teaching these examples in the formation of planetary thinking in students, the formation of logical, critical and creative thinking, the study of selected examples from world literature, the formation of cognitive and communication skills were emphasized. The study noted that the formation of national-human ideas among students, the development of personality is one of the main requirements of modern subject programs. Of great scientific and methodological importance is the formation of a planetary image of the younger generation, the establishment of artistic and literary parallelism in literature lessons in the direction of fostering a sense of unity and faith in the world.

Key words: world literature, foreign literature, comparative teaching, methodology of teaching literature, parallel teaching methods, planetary thinking, education in the post-pandemic period.

Introduction

The world is now becoming a single spiritual space. It is impossible to imagine any area in isolation from other places. This situation is especially evident in the sphere of education and culture. Of course, there are individual and different problems and disadvantages of such common approaches and common existence. Both local events and global changes in any geographic region of the world affect the overall global socio-political, scientific thought, change the rhythm of human life, and so on. The environmental, political, social, humanitarian and cultural problems of the world community, which have reached a serious global level, must be addressed by the younger generation currently studying in general education schools. They should even see this as a serious problem that

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needs to be addressed, and understand the scope of their responsibilities. For this reason, it is very important to contribute to the formation of a broad view of the world in high school, to instill in students an unquenchable interest in the artistic achievements of other peoples.

Improving literary education in secondary school involves the formation of new approaches to the teaching of literature. The modern schoolboy is faced with the need to master and systematize a large amount of information from various fields of science, culture and social relations. At the same time, experts are well aware that without clarifying the system of relations of the Azerbaijani literary world with world literature, without assessing the dimensions, scale and system of our literary-aesthetic thinking, worldview, the horizons of the world literary process can not be imagined. It is difficult. The way out is to carefully study the samples of world literature during literature lessons, to study literature in the classroom, extracurricular activities, extracurricular activities, as well as, if necessary, in extracurricular activities within a special course within the limits of Azerbaijani literature. The aim of the literature is to study in depth and meaningfully, to analyze, to identify similarities and parallels. We need to know that when we work on materials dedicated to the in-depth study of the main trends and problems of the literary process, the urgency and necessity of this topic becomes apparent. At the same time, the perfect student personality is an integrative special course, the work - on the content level of literary-artistic, historical-literary and cultural information during the faculty, the unification of national and humanistic information and values in the implementation of state standards, the principle of education can be realized during the reunion with. Thus, with the effective teaching of world literature on the basis of Azerbaijani literature, the integrity of the idea of the world artistic process is achieved, deep typological and contact links between Azerbaijani and foreign literature are identified and "planetary" thinking is formed.

It is an undeniable fact that the perspective development and future economic growth of nations and states, the material well-being of the population, the moral stability and contentment of citizens - directly depend on his education. Today's education is a key factor in the effective formation of the country's human resources and its productivity and quality in the coming decades. In modern times and conditions, the socio-natural, biological-medical phenomena, socio-economic, political-cultural situations or currents that can be remedied or cannot be taken on a global scale make it necessary for the education system to respond directly to innovative challenges. The creation of new foundations of subject programs, training technologies, education legislation, the formation of flexible and effective mechanisms in this context is one of the conditions for the future of modern political structures. Global geopolitics, technological and systematic potential structural changes in financial systems, the formation of new world economic centers, the development of capital markets, e-commerce, digital economy, new realities of supply and demand in the global market, the need for competitive personnel, as well as other crucial factors should be the main topic of discussion in education today.

In the post-pandemic period, the values of human life have increased in quality and quantity, the content and structure have changed, living standards have become more complex, new social and economic, political relations have been formed, globalization and planetary thinking are rapidly becoming a modern paradigm. There is a need for modern pedagogical science, and new questions are posed to training and education. The subject of literature has a wide range of opportunities in the formation of hypotheses and research in these questions. For example, now everyone, from people with simple knowledge and skills to the heads of large corporations, has access to the world's incredibly vast information using the limitlessness of the Internet, no matter where they are. "Today, there are constant changes in public life, science and technology. Abundance of information, globalization, the Internet, the formation of a single educational space, integration into the European educational space, new learning technologies, etc. These issues need to be addressed in the content of education, as well as in teaching, methods and assessment. That is why the optimal option is to

update the educational documents for a period of 5 years. Carrying out these changes every five years appears as a necessity "(F. Yusifov, "Methods of teaching literature", Baku, 2017, pp. 26-27).

Observations and surveys show that our difficulties in teaching literature are greater than in other disciplines. When teachers analyze works of art and organize students' mastery, in many cases there are difficulties and confusing moments. When we look at the examples of world literature from the geographical position of Azerbaijan, there are confusions and misinterpretations regarding the teaching of the so-called Western literature, because it stands in the west. These difficulties are related to philological, didactic and psychological aspects of teaching. When we add the realities of Azerbaijan's historical experience, the real picture emerges. The psychological, philological and didactic difficulties that arise in the Azerbaijani school today, especially in connection with the teaching of literature, are due to the influence of the main trends of the Soviet era. The literature of the world still refers to the non-protection of the interests of the working masses, the class struggle, the exploitation of peasant labor, the communist ideology and the Bolshevik ideology, which, although their names have been erased from the list, remain in our schools. These approaches are fresh in various forms and contents and have deep roots. This tendency, which is inextricably linked with the historical aspect and experience, was, of course, difficult to reverse. But it shouldn't have lasted that long. For example, let me tell you about an unpleasant appearance. This is due to the V-XI class literature textbooks currently used in Azerbaijani secondary schools. You may also find it interesting and strange that the world school of world literature, especially western literature, still includes only Jack Lon Don, Mark Twain (V class), Alexander Dumas (VI class), Victor Hugo (VII) during V-XI class. class), E. Heminquey (class XI) gets acquainted with several works that do not characterize their creativity (except E. Heminquey). If you think about it, these names are the authors who were allowed to teach some of their works during the Soviet era. He wanted to give the impression that the works of dozens of Soviet literary critics translated into the languages of the Soviet peoples depicted the vortices of human life, the turmoil, the moral crisis of the individual, and that all the blame lay with the capitalist exploiting class. Poverty and misery, tears and deprivation are purely anti-democratic in the West. Thus, the Soviet ideology wanted to tell the peoples of the USSR that we all live well, but the capitalist world is starving. Professor Cedric Watts, in an introduction to one of the published books on O. Henry, wrote about O. Henry's popularity in the USSR: Because he has repeatedly described Americans living only in their mouths, where the wealth of many people has prevailed over the needy "(Cedric Watts, O. Henry. 2012, p.26).

We need to take a brief look at history to describe the causes and depth of the landscape. From April 28, 1920 to October 18, 1991, Azerbay lived for 71 years as a member of a huge empire called the USSR. In these prisons, economic and political orders were not limited to Moscow. All official textbooks and teaching aids taught in the country were carefully checked, sent directly to the red capital, adapted to the requirements of Bolshevism, and presented to schools as a key factor in ideological weapons.

How did this situation come about? A few years after the occupation of Azerbaijan by the Soviet army, in the late 1920s, the Soviet leadership launched a direct attack on fiction that was outside the communist ideology and did not support that position. The control of the central apparatus in the field of literature began to strengthen. The establishment of various creative organizations during this period was the result of that administrative system of administration. Thus, the famous party resolutions and decisions of 1925 "On the policy of the party in the field of literature", "On the reorganization of literary and artistic organizations" of 1932, as well as the unification of writers in different societies and unions on ideological orientation (1925 "Young Golden Pens", "Golden Pens" from 1926, "Azerbaijan Proletarian Writers' Society" from 1927, Azerbaijan Soviet Writers' Union from 1934 and finally the USSR Writers' Union) slowed down the flight of free inspiration and creative imagination. was an obstacle to the progress "(Alishanoglu T, 2006, p. 144).

In the 1930s, collectivization began in all spheres in the USSR. Peasants were concentrated in collective and state farms, industries in industrial centers, and writers and other artists in various unions and associations. This simplifies administrative management, speeds up the execution of orders from the center, quickly and accurately identifies external trends, and effective prevention policy . (Olena P. 2011)

The result soon showed itself. Soviet internal terror began. Now, looking at the 1920s, the second half of the 1930s is remembered as a "red terror" vortex. There are opinions and sources that 3 million to 10 million people were killed during the Soviet repressions. (See: 1. "Victims of the Soviet Penal System in the Pre-war Years: A First Approach on the Basis of Archival Evidence" . Archived from the original on 2008-06-11.Snyder, Timothy (2011-01-27). 2. "Hitler vs. Stalin: Who Was Worse?" . The New York Review of Books . Retrieved 2019-05-28) In the 1930s , the shooting, execution , and deportation of hundreds of thousands of dissidents in Azerbaijan alone was a "major cleansing" operation. The physical destruction of so many people was aimed at creating a new communist reality. Imagine that a new reality and ideology was created by the physical destruction of hundreds of thousands of free-thinking people throughout the USSR. "Since the 1920s," proletarian "literature and, more broadly, the" proletarian culture "movement have flourished in the north of Azerbaijan. It is true that this movement was organized from "above", but it must be admitted that the masses did not seriously resist this organization. In the 1930s, the ideological foundations of "proletarian literature" were already laid, writers who did not accept it were annihilated, and literary work became "part of the general proletarian work." And so, in the North (we are talking about Northern Azerbaijan occupied by the USSR.) Literature created the image of "the Azerbaijani people who built communism" (Jafarov N. 2001, p., 56) And the examples of local and even world literature presented to the people at that time were intended to justify these bloody crimes. Also, the translation of foreign literature into Azerbaijani and its use as a teaching resource was influenced by the same logic.

But now there are no difficulties and limitations. On the contrary, for a long time, even now, students have been unaware of the main ideas and content of world literature, the main literary trends, currents and schools that shape the general appearance and goals of the world humanitarian arena. But what steps are needed to address the current landscape? It seems that in our secondary schools we still have a lot of work to do with the works presented to students.

We have been separated from the closed regime for 30 years, but our textbooks and sources , resources and their content have not been completely separated from those realities. So, at what level and in what content do we need innovations and challenges?

The duties and responsibilities of literature specialists, textbook authors, and subject methodologists are now many. The cultural achievements of modern peoples formed over thousands of years and absorbed into their behavior, ethno-religious behavior and intellects, must be so effective and own that the Azerbaijani youth is able to consciously capture the cultural achievements and genesis of the changing world. , determine the map of intellectual movement .

World public opinion and technical achievements are currently at their highest (in time!) Stage, and this trend continues to grow. "We are talking about the fundamental justification of human existence, the creation of new values. The initial foundations of a new worldview are already emerging within man-made civilization. In the modern world, completely different cultural traditions collide, confront and enter into dialogue. And humanity understands that it is necessary to learn to conduct this dialogue "(Nain A.Ya.1995, p.123).

The content of education at school based on national and human values is the main quality - factor that will ensure the future development of the people, the quality of education, the welfare of the

population . The development of the student's personality and thinking are the criteria that will ensure the country's labor market, the intellectual sphere, the training of competitive personnel , the quality of human resources. "The next strategic task facing the country is to ensure sustainable economic development and improve the living standards of the population by further modernizing socio-economic life and adapting it to best international practices. Modernization is primarily associated with the successful application of advanced technologies and management methods, innovations based on scientific achievements in the socio-economic life of the country. The priority for this is to accelerate the integration of the country's economy into the world economy , as well as the development of human capital in the country, ensuring the acquisition of modern knowledge and skills. The development of human capital is one of the most important conditions for the successful integration of the economy into the global system and the country's more effective use of international competition, and is a key task of the country's education system "(State Strategy for Education Development in Azerbaijan).

Systematic and comparative teaching of examples of world literature will seriously serve to raise the level of teaching the subject of literature, to implement standards more effectively, and to ensure the interest of students .

Vernadsky claimed that the importance of the "planetary" worldview, ie the attitude to the environment from the point of view of the inhabitants of the planet Earth, based on the principles of the world rather than the narrow world (Vernadsky VI Thoughts of a naturalist. In 2 kn. -M., 1975. - 173,191 p.). For this reason, the scientist considered it necessary to teach exemplary works of world literature in secondary schools.

The use of foreign literature, successful literary works, which are the main source of human values and examples, has a significant impact on improving the quality of education. The student gets acquainted with the national literary samples, masters them, masters the logical burden presented by the writer, the example of folklore, and at the same time acquires more comprehensive and deeper knowledge and skills by mastering the content of the world literature.

Homer's "Odyssey" with "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" epics, "Iliad", ancient Indian epics with "Koroglu" epos, Nizami Ganjavi and U.Shakespeare, Greek mythology - Azerbaijan mythical system, "Avesta" with the pantheon of Greek gods, Twelfth century Azerbaijani renaissance and European renaissance, 19th century MFAkhundzadeh in French literature Moliere, J. Mammadguluzade, A. - Hagverdiyev, O. Henry, Mark Twain, Anar, Elchin, U. Faulkner, E. Hemingway, QGM Mark The analysis and teaching of the main examples of modern Azerbaijani literature in the form of mutual comparison, of course, within the possibilities provided by the secondary school literature course, can only benefit the Azerbaijani school.

It has great opportunities in shaping the student's personality, his spiritual world and aesthetic taste . Pupils acquire an active position in life by understanding and evaluating the complex events and realities of life reflected in the work of art. In this sense, literature lessons should be approached as life and spiritual lessons, a type of cognitive activity. Fiction is a special form of spiritual communication. A student who reads a perfect work of art, thinks about the moral and aesthetic problems raised there, comments on the fate of the heroes, the position of the artist, becomes an interviewer of a powerful artist, enriches himself spiritually by studying his thoughts and ideas. In this process, it is possible to assess the activities, actions and behavior of students in terms of moral and aesthetic norms "(A. Garabagli. 1968, p.44.).

The comparative teaching of some selected examples of ancient Sumerian, ancient Egyptian, ancient Jewish, ancient Chinese, ancient Greek and Roman literature in the teaching of ancient Azerbaijani literature can play an important role in the development of students' cognitive and

communication skills. In parallel, this issue plays a special role in terms of creating integration between the subject of literature and general history, the formation of competencies in both subjects. For example, in ancient Egyptian literature there is a "tale of a shipwreck." This fairy tale is about a hero who lived far away from his homeland for a long time, longed for his homeland and then returned to it. The content of this example seems to convey to the reader the main ideas of Azerbaijani literature.

What is the result of the presentation of the above facts: the student receives information about the culture and literature of the peoples of the world, this information helps to master the historical themes of that period. This information is consistently continued in the upper classes. The student hears the names of famous figures of world literature, is briefed on the literature of different nations. This information can be considered serious material for the formation of the student's worldview. At the same time, it plays an important role in the formation of literary knowledge. Therefore, in the subject of "Literature" there is a need to include examples of literature of different foreign nations in the teaching, to make comparisons. "Discussion of Azerbaijani literature, as well as selected examples from the literature of the peoples of the world in various classes of literature allows students to understand and evaluate the moral and aesthetic problems of modern times, changes in life and society, to master national and universal moral values " (General of Azerbaijan republic literature education program for schools (V-XI classes).

Many scientific researches have been carried out that the main ideas and themes of Azerbaijani literature are spread in many countries of the world, and it is both typological and mutual benefit. "The main feature that characterizes the process of world history in modern times is globalization. Attempts to bring the countries and peoples of the world closer together have accelerated integration in the socio-political, economic and cultural spheres to such an extent that it has led to the formation of a planetary mindset, as well as responsibility for the fate of the planet "(M. Babayev, 2009, p.7). The scientist has prepared a serious and fact-based scientific monograph on the influence of Nasimi's work on the work of American transcendentalists.

"The propagation of Sufi philosophical views through poetry was a practical experience for American transcendentalists. Poems published by transcendentalists have been formed as a new form of artistic protest against American Orthodox Calvinism and materialists "(M.Babayev., 2009, p.17).

The fact that the main ideas, thoughts and goals of our literature do not lag behind the literature of the developed nations of the world, whether the idea, the content or the talent of the writer, shows the strength and power of Azerbaijani literature. Knowing these features of the student will increase his respect for the literature and history of his people.

Proximity of motif and plot of "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud epics" similar to examples of world literature, proximity of plot of "Koroglu" epos in literature of many nations, typological "kinship" of images, wide appeal to Nizami Ganjavi's ideas in the world, 70 years of Soviet repression, Bolshevik machine Despite the obstacles , the establishment of relations between Azerbaijani literature and world literature can be an indicator of the strength and power of our people, as well as an indicator of the student's confidence in himself and his nation.

Azerbaijani education is currently experiencing a new period of creation and development, gaining new content qualities and benefiting from the proven experience of progressive educational achievements of developed countries. The education policy based on national and human values is in the logic and practice of the implemented reforms. Russell Bertrand, an English philosopher, mathematician, and public figure who won the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1950, wrote, "Education must have two purposes: to cultivate intelligence on the one hand, and to cultivate citizenship on the other." (What we expect from knowledge. Istanbul, 1962) and this reflects many important issues.

So, parallel, comparative teaching of literary works can give our students the following:

1. Students' planetary thinking is formed, the idea that the world is a single space is strengthened;
2. The ideas and content of our national literature can be revised more accurately and correctly.
3. There will be more effective implementation of state standards on the subject of literature;
4. As a result of the analysis and comparison of literary works formed in different geographical and cultural spaces, students' logical, critical and creative thinking will be formed and developed more correctly;
5. Students' interest in literature lessons is better ensured.

We think that in the coming years, when preparing literary subject curricula and writing textbooks, preference will be given to materials that allow the parallel teaching of examples of world literature, as well as examples of national literature. At the same time, parallel comparisons will be given more space when literature teachers teach the subject.

References

1. Ahmadov H., Zeynalova N. (2016). Pedagogy, Baku, Science and Education
2. Asadov A. (2017). US-Azerbaijani literary relations: a new prose. Baku, "Khan" Publishing House
3. Babayev M. (2009) John Steinbeck's work in a comparative context with Azerbaijani literature ", Baku
4. Educational program on the subject of literature for secondary schools of the Republic of Azerbaijan (curriculum) (v-xi classes). (2012) Baku
5. Hasanli B. (2016) Methods of teaching literature, Baku
6. Hasanova G. (2013). Literary translation and Azerbaijan-US literary relations, Baku
7. Karabakh A. (1968) Methods of teaching literature, Baku, Maarif
8. Nine A.Ya. (1995), Innovations in education. Chelyabinsk
9. Özbek Y. (2014) *Bencilik Ne Güzel Şey*. 1.Vol. Baskı, Çizgi Kitabevi.
10. Pashayev A.H. Rustamov F.A. Pedagogy (2010). Baku, Science and Education publishing house
11. Pashayev AH, Rustamov F.A. (2010) Pedagogy, Baku, Science and Education publishing house
12. Pieter Vermeulen & Amélie Hurkens (2020) The Americanization of World Literature?, *Interventions*, 22:3, 433-450, DOI: 10.1080/1369801X.2019.1659166
13. Reform: research, results, (2011) Translator, Baku
14. Rostenkowski D. (1981). Economic Recovery Tax Act of 1981. USC
15. Russel Bertrand. (1962) What we expect from knowledge. Istanbul
16. Rustamli A. (2011). Translator Jafar Jabbarli, Baku, Ozan

17. Saleh M. Al-Salman & Asad Al-Ghalith (2019) Translation as a means of internationalization: the case for world literature, *Asia Pacific Translation and Intercultural Studies*, 6:3, 189-203, DOI: 10.1080/23306343.2019.1687078
18. State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan
19. Suleymanova A. (2014) Content standard in subject curricula, *Curriculum*
20. Suleymanova A. (2014) Basics of education, Baku: "Education, 2014
21. Suzanne Conklin Akbari (2017) Modeling medieval world literature, *Middle Eastern Literatures*, 20:1, 2-17, DOI: 10.1080/1475262X.2017.1303985
22. Textbook "General History" for secondary schools VI classes, 2017, Baku
23. Textbook "Literature" for secondary schools X class, (2018) Baku
24. Valehov J. (2015). National education in the process of modern transformational - processes (socio-philosophical analysis), Baku, Education
25. Yusifov F. (2017), Methods of teaching literature, Baku, 304 p.